

Assessment of Micronutrient Content in Fortified Foods: A Comparative Study of Labelled Claims versus Laboratory Analysis

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Abstract

Food fortification is a crucial strategy to combat micronutrient deficiencies, ensuring that populations receive essential vitamins and minerals. This study assessed the accuracy of micronutrient content in fortified foods sold in Kebbi State by comparing labeled claims with laboratory analysis results. A total of 20 fortified food samples, including rice, pasta, flour, vegetable oil, sugar, and salt, were analyzed for key micronutrients using Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometry (AAS) and standard AOAC methods for vitamin determination. The results revealed significant discrepancies between labeled claims and actual micronutrient content. For instance, Vitamin A in fortified rice ranged from 798.30±19.12 IU/kg to undetectable levels, far below the Standard requirement of 25,000 IU/kg. Similarly, iron concentrations varied from 6.55±0.43 mg/kg to 152.77±0.38 mg/kg, with inconsistencies across different products. Statistical analysis showed differences between labeled claims and laboratory results for several micronutrients. These findings highlight the need for stricter regulatory enforcement and improved quality control measures in fortified food production. It is recommended that routine monitoring and compliance checks be strengthened to ensure the effectiveness of fortification programs in addressing micronutrient deficiencies.

Keywords: Compliance Check, Food Fortification, Micronutrient Deficiencies, Minerals, Vitamins

1.0 Introduction

Food fortification refers to the intentional addition of essential nutrients to food products to correct or prevent deficiencies within a population. According to the World Health Organization (WHO) and the Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO), fortification enhances the nutritional quality of food supplies while offering significant public health benefits. While the body requires vitamins and minerals for growth, immunity, and metabolic functions, deficiencies in these nutrients can result in serious health consequences, including cognitive impairments, weakened immunity, and chronic diseases [1,2,3].

Various food fortification strategies exist, including biofortification (enhancing nutrient content in crops through breeding or biotechnology), industrial fortification (adding nutrients during manufacturing), and home fortification (supplementing meals with micronutrient powders). In regions where staple diets lack essential micronutrients due to soil conditions or dietary limitations, fortification serves as a cost-effective approach to preventing widespread deficiency diseases [5, 6].

Despite global efforts to improve nutritional intake through food fortification, evidence suggests that many fortified food products fail to meet the required nutrient levels. Commonly fortified foods include cereals, dairy products, oils, and

condiments [7]. However, studies indicate that gaps in regulatory oversight and variations in fortification practices can lead to unreliable nutrient content in such products. Addressing these issues is critical to ensuring that fortified foods effectively deliver the intended health benefits [8].

Micronutrient deficiencies, particularly in vitamins and minerals such as iron, vitamin A, iodine, folate, and zinc, remain a significant public health concern in Nigeria, especially among women of reproductive age and children under five [9]. These deficiencies can lead to severe health issues, including anemia, impaired cognitive development, weakened immunity, and increased morbidity and mortality rates [10].

To combat these challenges, large-scale food fortification (LSFF) has been recognized as a cost-effective strategy to improve the nutritional quality of food supplies. In Nigeria, efforts have been made to fortify staple foods such as wheat flour, maize flour, sugar, and vegetable oil with essential micronutrients. However, the implementation and monitoring of these fortification programs have faced challenges, including regulatory enforcement, quality control, and compliance by food producers [11,12].

A recent application of the Grading of Recommendations Assessment, Development, and Evaluation (GRADE) framework to Nigeria's fortification program highlighted the need for evidence-informed decision-making to enhance program effectiveness [13]. The study emphasized the importance of involving policymakers, food processors, and development partners in designing and implementing fortification initiatives [14, 15].

In 2002 the World Health Report identified iodine, iron, vitamin A and zinc deficiencies as being among the world's most serious health risk factors. The four key strategies identified to address Micronutrient Deficiency are: dietary improvement, supplementation, fortified food and global public health and other disease control measures [16,17]. Food fortification is recognized as one of the most cost effective methods. Short-term strategies such as nutrient supplementation (giving a large dose of the micronutrient as a medicinal supplement) have been effective in providing immediate relief in several countries, but this approach was not sustainable in the long term. The World Bank, WHO, UNICEF, Micronutrient Initiative (MI) and Global Alliance for Improved Nutrition (GAIN) also have identified fortification,

as among the most cost-effective of all health interventions and fortification of staple foods with micronutrients is the strategy gaining momentum currently in many developing countries [18,19].

Their functions include energy production and metabolism, immune system support, growth and development, antioxidant functions, nervous system function, bone health, eye health, skin, hair, and nail health. They are mostly gotten from food sources like fruits and vegetables, whole grains, legumes, nuts and seeds, dairy products and fortified foods. Their Deficiency risks include fatigue and weakness, impaired growth and development, weakened immune system, poor wound healing and increased risk of chronic diseases. But adequate micronutrient intake is crucial for maintaining optimal health. A well-balanced diet that includes a variety of whole foods can provide sufficient micronutrients. However, supplements may be necessary in cases of deficiency or increased demand [19].

Despite the widespread fortification of staple foods with micronutrients, a significant proportion of fortified foods fail to meet the recommended levels of micronutrients, posing a risk to public health [20]. The inconsistent levels of micronutrients in fortified foods can lead to: inadequate prevention of micronutrient deficiencies, inefficient use of resources for fortification, erosion of consumer trust in fortified foods, potential health risks due to excessive intake of certain micronutrients [21].

There is still a growing concern about the accuracy and reliability of the micronutrient content claims on fortified food labels. Inaccurate labeling can lead to misguided consumption patterns and ineffective nutritional interventions as determined by laboratory analysis. Discrepancies between labeled claims and actual content can undermine public health efforts aimed at reducing micronutrient deficiencies and quality control measures in ensuring the accuracy of micronutrient labeling. Identifying gaps and weaknesses in these systems is essential for recommending improvements that can enhance the reliability of fortified food products.

This study will assess the effectiveness of existing regulatory frameworks and quality control measures in ensuring the accuracy of micronutrient labeling. Food fortification should encompass important micronutrient-fortified foods (M-FF) supply on the national market as well as the consumption patterns of the food products by different population groups. Discrepancies between

labeled claims and actual micronutrient content can lead to mistrust and reduced confidence in fortified foods. This study will provide evidence to verify the authenticity of the claims, thereby helping to restore and maintain consumer trust.

Accurate labeling is also essential for ensuring that individuals receive the correct amount of nutrients to meet their dietary needs, thereby safeguarding public health. By confirming the claims labeled and the actual micronutrients content, the food manufacturers are motivated to adhere to the labeling regulations and maintain high standards of quality control. This can lead to overall improvements in the production and labeling of fortified foods.

This study will contribute to the broader scientific understanding of food fortification and nutrient labeling. The comparative analysis of labeled claims versus laboratory analysis will add to the existing body of research, providing insights that

can be applied in other regions and contexts. This will support global efforts to combat micronutrient deficiencies through fortified foods. The aim of this study was to assess the accuracy of micronutrient content claims on fortified food labels in Kebbi metropolis and assess the quality compliance of fortified foods with recommended standard and regulations.

2.0 Materials and Methods

Samples Selection

A total of twenty (20) fortified food samples comprising seven (7) brands of Rice, three (3) pastas, four (4) flours, three (3) vegetable oils, two (2) sugars and one (1) salt were randomly selected for different retailers in Kebbi metropolis and laboratory analysis were performed in triplicate to ensure accuracy and precision. The selected fortified food samples were presented in (Table 1).

Table 1: The Fortified Food Sample, Sample Identification Number, Claimed Minerals and Vitamins

Food Category	Sample Identification Number	Minerals Claimed	Vitamins Claimed
Rice	RIC-01	Sodium, Calcium, Iron	Vitamin A, B ₁ , B ₉
	RIC-02	Iron, Manganese	Vitamin A, B ₁ , B ₉
	RIC-03	Iron, Calcium, Sodium, Magnesium	Vitamin B ₁ , B ₃ , B ₆ , B ₉
	RIC-04	Iron, Calcium, Sodium	Vitamin B ₁ , B ₃ , B ₆ , B ₉
	RIC-05	Iron, Manganese, Calcium, Potassium	Vitamin B ₁ , B ₃ , B ₆ , B ₉
	RIC-06	Iron, Sodium, Calcium, Potassium	Vitamin B ₁ , B ₃ , B ₆ , B ₉
	RIC-07	Iron, Potassium, Calcium, Selenium	Vitamin B ₁ , B ₃
Pastas	PAS-01	Iron, Calcium, Sodium, Potassium	Vitamin B ₁ , B ₃ , B ₆ , B ₉
	PAS-02	Iron, Calcium	Vitamin A, B ₁ , B ₂ , B ₆ , B ₉
	PAS-03	Potassium, Iron, Sodium	Vitamin B ₁ , B ₃ , B ₆ , B ₉
Flours	FLO-01	Iron, Zinc, Phosphorus, Magnesium	Vitamin A, B ₁ , B ₆ , B ₁₂
	FLO-02	Zinc, Iron, Calcium	Vitamin A, B ₁ , B ₂ , B ₆ , B ₉ , B ₁₂
	FLO-03	Calcium, Potassium, Magnesium, Phosphorous, Iron	Vitamin A, B ₁ , B ₆ , B ₉
	FLO-04	Zinc, Iron, Phosphorus, Magnesium	Vitamin B ₁ , B ₆ , B ₉
Vegetable Oils	VEO-01	Calcium, Phosphorus	Vitamin A, D, K
	VEO-02	Calcium, Sodium, Phosphorus, Magnesium, Potassium	Vitamin A, D, K
	VEO-03	Calcium, Phosphorus,	Vitamin A, D
Sugar	SUG-01	Sodium	Vitamin A
	SUG-02	Calcium, Iron, Potassium	Vitamin A
Salt	SLT-01	Sodium, Iodine	

Mineral Determination

The mineral content of the samples was determined by weighing 2g of each sample into a clean and dried crucible. The crucible was placed in a muffle furnace at 550°C for 3 hours [22]. The crucible was allowed to cool in a desiccator and the resulting ash was digested with 10ml of 10% HCl and filtered in 50ml standard flask [22]. The filtrate was made up to the meniscus with deionized water. The blank was also prepared by taking 10ml of 10% HCl and made up to 50ml. The solution was aspirated into Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometer (AAS Buck 235) for determination of mineral present in the samples [22].

Vitamin Determination

Determination of Vitamin A

A 5g of sample was mixed with 30ml absolute alcohol and 3ml of 5% potassium hydroxide boil gently under reflux for 30min in a stream of oxygen free nitrogen. The mixture was cooled and 30ml water was transferred to UV-Vis Spectrophotometer (Model 6800, Shimadzu, Japan), wash in with 3X50ml ether and extract the vitamin A by shaking for 1min. The supernatant was discarded and the extract were washed with 4X50ml water and then mixed cautiously during the first two washes to avoid emulsion formation [23]. The washed extract was evaporated down to about 5ml and the remaining ether was then removed in a stream of nitrogen at room temperature. The residue were dissolved in sufficient isopropyl alcohol to give a solution containing 9-15 units per ml and the extinctions was measured at 300, 310, 325 and 334nm and the wavelength of maximum absorption [23].

Determination of Vitamin B₁ (Thiamine)

A 5g of the weighed sample was homogenized with 50ml 0.2M ethanoic sodium hydroxide and then filtered into a 100ml conical flask and 10ml of the filtrate was pipetted and the colour was developed by addition of 10ml of 1% potassium dichromate and absorbance was read at 360nm. A blank solution is also prepared [24].

Determination of Vitamin B₂ (Riboflavin)

A 5g of the weighed sample was extracted with 100ml of 50% ethanol and shaken for one hour. This was filtered into 100ml flask and 10ml of the

extract and then pipetted into 50ml volumetric flask. Exactly 10ml of 5% potassium permanganate and 10ml of 30% H₂O₂ were added and allowed to stand over a hot water bath for 30min [24]. Two (2) ml of 40% sodium sulphate was added. This was made up to 50ml mark and the absorbance was measured at 510nm using UV-Vis Spectrophotometer (Model 6800, Shimadzu, Japan) [24].

Determination of Vitamin B₃ (Niacin)

A 5g of the weighed sample was treated with 50ml 1N H₂SO₄ and shaken for 30min. Three drops of ammonia solution were added to the sample and filtered. The filtrate was pipette into a 50ml volumetric flask and 5ml of potassium cyanide was added. This was acidified with 5ml of 0.02N H₂SO₄ and absorbance was measure using spectrophotometer at 470nm [24].

Determination of Vitamin B₆

To a 10ml volumetric flask, 20mg of the sample was added and then dissolved with 0.1N HCl. 5ml of the standard and sampled hydrolysis solution was taken in marked test tubes [24]. In each test tube, 1ml of ammonium buffer, 1ml of 20% Sodium Acetate, 1ml of 5% Boric acid and 1ml dye (2, 6 dichloroquinoneChloroimide) solution were added. The absorbance was recorded as 650nm against the blank. A plot of vitamin standard was done and the amounts of vitamin B₆ present in the samples were computed from its calibration curve [24].

Determination of Vitamin B₉ (Folic Acid)

Vitamin B₉ was determined spectrophotometrically using a modified standard method of [25]. homogenized samples powder (500mg) was weighed into 100ml volumetric flask and dissolved with 50ml, 3% of disodium hydrogen orthorhosphate, shaken for 20 minutes and made up to the meniscus with the same solution and then filtered (Whatman No.1 Filter Paper). The standard folic acid powder (28mg) was weighed and treated as above. The filtrate (40ml) was taken from the test and 3ml of the filtrate was taken from the standard and each into separate 100ml volumetric flask and was made up to mark with 3% disodium hydrogen orthorhosphate.

Five milliliters of both standard and test each was added into 50ml volumetric flask and was treated for $\pm\mu$ colour development as follows:

1. Two milliliters of KMNO₄ (0.4%) was added and allowed to stand for one minute
2. Two milliliters of sodium nitrate (2%) was added.
3. Two milliliters of 5M HCl was also added and both standard and test was shaken.
4. Two milliliters of sulphuric acid (5%).
5. 2 ml of sodium acetate/EDTA (5%) was added, shake and allow to stand for 10 minutes.
6. Two milliliters of Azodye (0.1%w/v) was added and allowed to stand for 10 minutes and absorbance read at 550 nm.

Potency

$$= \frac{AT}{AS} \times \frac{WS}{WT} \times \frac{3}{100} \times \frac{100}{40} \times \text{Average Fill Weight}$$

AT = Absorbance of test.

AS = Absorbance of standard.

WS = Weight of standard.

WT = Weight of test.

Average fill weight = 480mg

Determination of Vitamin D

Vitamin D content was determined by mixing the carr-price reagent (20% m/v of antimony trichloride in chloroform with 40% pure acetylchloride freshly prepared and free from alcohol. 9ml of the carr-price was added to 1ml of sample extracted with chloroform and the extinction was measured at 500nm against reagent blank. The concentration was extrapolated from standard curve graph using vitamin D standard [24].

Determination of Vitamin K

Vitamin K sample was determined by exactly 0.2g of sample was added to 5ml of ethanol and the sample extract with the 50ul of 1% potassium ferrocyanide was incubated in the dark for 45 min. The absorbance were read at 680 nm step by step [24].

Statistical Analysis

Analyses were carried out in triplicates of each set up. The data were expressed as mean±standard deviation (SD). T-test was performed to compare

for significance difference ($p < 0.05$) between micronutrients in the fortified food product and Standard Requirement. Values were analysed using the SPSS statistical package.

3.0 Results

The results in Table 2 revealed that Vitamin A was found in only two samples (RIC-01 and RIC-02), while the remaining samples had no detectable levels. Additionally, Vitamins B3 and B6 were not detected in some samples. Only RIC-01 and RIC-02 contained Vitamin A (but much lower than the required 25,000 IU/kg). Vitamin B1 (Thiamine) was present in all samples but still below the 6.00 mg/kg standard. Vitamin B3 (Niacin) and Vitamin B6 (Pyridoxine) were undetectable in some samples. Vitamin B9 (Folic Acid) was present but inconsistent across samples. Compared to standard requirements, the vitamin levels showed significant differences ($p < 0.05$) from the standard requirements.

Table 3 shows that Vitamin A was detected in two samples (PAS-02 and PAS-03), although at significantly lower levels than the standard. Vitamin B1 and B6 levels varied among samples, but none reached the required standards. PAS-01 had no detectable Vitamin A, while PAS-02 and PAS-03 had low levels. Vitamin B1 was detected, but PAS-03 had an abnormally low level (0.09 mg/kg) compared to others. Vitamin B3 was detected at lower levels than the 45.00 mg/kg standard. Vitamin A, B1, B3, and B9 showed significant differences ($p < 0.05$) from the standard requirements.

Table 4 shows that some samples contained Vitamin A, while others did not. B2 and B12 were undetectable in some cases, showing inconsistent fortification. Vitamin A was found in some samples, but others had no detectable levels. Flour contained Vitamin B12, which was absent in rice and pasta. Vitamin B2 (Riboflavin) was undetectable in some samples. Flour was the only food tested that contained Vitamin B12. Most vitamins showed significant differences ($p < 0.05$) from the standard requirements.

Table 2: Concentrations of Vitamins in Fortified Rice Samples compared with Standard Requirement.

Food Category	Sample Identification Number	Vitamin A (iu/kg)	Vitamin B ₁ (mg/kg)	Vitamin B ₃ (mg/kg)	Vitamin B ₆ (mg/kg)	Vitamin B ₉ (mg/kg)
Rice	RIC-01	798.30±19.12 ^a	0.72±0.12 ^a	ND	ND	5.92±0.14 ^a
	RIC-02	679.08±16.26 ^b	0.75±0.02 ^b	ND	ND	7.04±0.17 ^b
	RIC-03	ND	0.75±0.12 ^c	1.78±0.05 ^a	6.78±0.16 ^a	6.43±0.62 ^c
	RIC-04	ND	0.72±0.02 ^d	1.78±0.05 ^b	7.64±0.18 ^b	6.57±0.53 ^d
	RIC-05	ND	0.73±0.02 ^e	1.89±0.05 ^c	3.35±0.08 ^c	6.78±0.58 ^e
	RIC-06	ND	0.73±0.02 ^f	1.77±0.05 ^d	7.43±0.17 ^d	6.71±0.17 ^f
	RIC-07	ND	0.71±0.02 ^g	1.77±0.05 ^e	ND	ND
*Standard Requirement		25,000.00 ^{a,b}	6.00 ^{a,b,c,d,e,f,g}	45.00 ^{a,b,c,d,e}	6.00 ^{a,b,c,d}	2.60 ^{a,b,c,d,e,f}

Values were expressed as mean±standard deviation. * T-test was performed to compare for significance difference (p<0.05) between micronutrients in the fortified food product and Standard Requirement. *Standard requirements are specified by NAFDAC as contained in the national fortification regulations act of 2021 (NAFDAC, 2021) * Not Detected (ND).

Table 3: Concentrations of Vitamins in Fortified Pasta Samples compared with Standard Requirement.

Food Category	Sample Identification Number	Vitamin A (iu/kg)	Vitamin B ₁ (mg/kg)	Vitamin B ₃ (mg/kg)	Vitamin B ₆ (mg/kg)	Vitamin B ₉ (mg/kg)
Pasta	PAS-01	ND	0.75±0.02 ^a	1.78±0.05 ^a	6.91±0.16 ^a	8.22±0.19 ^a
	PAS-02	478.98±11.47 ^a	0.74±0.12 ^b	0.42±0.01 ^b	4.43±0.10 ^b	7.94±0.19 ^b
	PAS-03	489.35±11.72 ^b	0.09±0.002 ^c	1.79±0.05 ^c	5.54±0.13 ^c	6.65±0.02 ^c
*Standard Requirement		25,000.00 ^{a,b}	6.00 ^{a,b,c}	45.00 ^{a,b,c}	6.00 ^{a,b,c}	2.60 ^{a,b,c}

Values were expressed as mean±standard deviation. * T-test was performed to compare for significance difference (p<0.05) between micronutrients in the fortified food product and Standard Requirement. *Standard requirements are specified by NAFDAC as contained in the national fortification regulations act of 2021 (NAFDAC, 2021) * Not Detected (ND).

Table 4: Concentrations of Vitamins in Fortified Flour Samples compared with Standard Requirement.

Food Category	Sample ID	Vitamin A (IU/Kg)	Vitamin B ₁ (mg/kg)	Vitamin B ₂ (mg/kg)	Vitamin B ₆ (mg/kg)	Vitamin B ₉ (mg/kg)	Vitamin B ₁₂ (mg/kg)
Flour	FLO-01	581.62±13.93 ^a	0.73±0.01 ^a	ND	4.54±0.10 ^a	ND	0.21±0.01 ^a
	FLO-02	ND	0.71±0.01 ^b	0.51±0.02 ^a	7.83±0.18 ^b	6.41±0.92 ^a	0.13±0.02 ^b
	FLO-03	509.04±12.19 ^b	0.73±0.01 ^c	ND	5.96±0.13 ^c	6.35±0.55 ^b	ND
	FLO-04	ND	ND	ND	7.12±0.16 ^d	6.42±0.77 ^c	ND
*Standard Requirement		25,000.00 ^{a,b}	6.00 ^{a,b,c}	45.00 ^a	6.00 ^{a,b,c,d}	2.60 ^{a,b,c}	2.60 ^{a,b}

Values were expressed as mean±standard deviation. * T-test was performed to compare for significance difference (p<0.05) between micronutrients in the fortified food product and Standard Requirement. *Standard requirements are specified by NAFDAC as contained in the national fortification regulations act of 2021 (NAFDAC, 2021) * Not Detected (ND).

Table 5 shows that all samples contained Vitamin A, but at much lower levels than the required 20,000 IU/kg. Additionally, the levels of Vitamin D and Vitamin K were significantly below the recommended standards. Low Vitamin A levels (383.60–504.90 IU/kg) compared to the 20,000 IU/kg standard. Vitamin D and K were present but at extremely low levels (far below the required

amounts). Vitamin A, D, and K showed significant differences (p<0.05) from the standard requirements. Only vegetable oil contained Vitamin D and Vitamin K.

The result obtained from Table 6 shows that both samples contained Vitamin A, but the levels shows significant differences (p<0.05) than the standard

requirement. Only Vitamin A was tested, and the levels (407.44–447.48 IU/kg) were much lower than the required 26,000 IU/kg.

The mineral levels in Table 7 varied significantly among samples. Some samples had undetectable levels of key minerals like potassium and

magnesium. Iron levels varied widely (6.55–104.50 mg/kg), with some samples above the required 50 mg/kg. Calcium levels were inconsistent, and potassium was mostly absent. Magnesium and manganese were present in some samples but not others. Calcium and sodium showed significant differences ($p < 0.05$) than the standard requirement.

Table 5: Concentrations of Vitamins in Fortified Vegetable Oil Samples compared with Standard Requirement.

Food Category	Sample Identification Number	Vitamin A (IU/Kg)	Vitamin D (mg/kg)	Vitamin K (mg/kg)
Vegetable Oil	VEO-01	383.60±9.18 ^a	0.21±0.01 ^a	0.04±0.003 ^a
	VEO-02	436.47±10.45 ^b	0.23±0.01 ^b	0.10±0.01 ^b
	VEO-03	504.90±12.09 ^c	0.36±0.01 ^c	ND
*Standard Requirement		20,000.00 ^{a,b,c}	25.00 ^{a,b,c}	2.00 ^{a,b}

Values were expressed as mean±standard deviation. * T-test was performed to compare for significance difference ($p < 0.05$) between micronutrients in the fortified food product and Standard Requirement. *Standard requirements are specified by NAFDAC as contained in the national fortification regulations act of 2021 (NAFDAC, 2021) * Not Detected (ND).

Table 6: Concentrations of vitamins in Fortified Sugar Samples compared with Standard Requirement.

Food Category	Sample Identification Number	Vitamin A
Sugar	SUG-01	447.478±0.80 ^a
	SUG-02	407.44±9.75 ^b
*Standard Requirement		26,000.00 ^{a,b}

Values were expressed as mean±standard deviation. *T-test was performed to compare for significance difference ($p < 0.05$) between micronutrients in the fortified food product and Standard Requirement. *Standard requirements are specified by NAFDAC as contained in the national fortification regulations act of 2021 (NAFDAC, 2021) * Not Detected (ND).

Table 7: Concentrations of Minerals in Fortified Rice Samples compared with Standard Requirement.

Food Cate gory	Sample Identifica tion No	Ca (mg/kg)	Fe (mg/kg)	Na (mg/kg)	K (mg/kg)	Mn (mg/kg)	Mg (mg/kg)
Rice	RIC-01	100.95±0.28 ^a	6.55±0.43 ^a	1507.16± 0.48 ^a	ND	ND	ND
	RIC-02	ND	15.27± 0.38 ^b	ND	ND	17.44±0.26 ^a	ND
	RIC-03	128.50±0.35 ^b	76.78±0.39 ^c	832.32±0.25 ^b	ND	ND	26.56± 0.26 ^a
	RIC-04	178.84±0.48 ^c	91.05±0.63 ^d	1110.26± 0.37 ^c	ND	ND	ND
	RIC-05	131.49±0.34 ^d	91.62±0.53 ^c	ND	1515.53±0.75 ^a	20.26±0.36 ^b	ND
	RIC-06	533.52±0.74 ^e	104.50±0.36 ^f	1192.76±0.36 ^d	ND	ND	ND
	RIC-07	205.83±0.34 ^f	101.77±0.32 ^g	ND	733.24±0.34 ^b	ND	ND
*NRVs (mg/kg)		1000.00 ^{a,b,c,d,e,f}	50.00 ^{a,b,c,d,e}	2000.00 ^{a,b,c,d}	2000.00 ^{a,b}	300.00 ^{a,b}	310.00 ^a

Key: Values were expressed as mean±standard deviation of triplicate measurements; *T-test was performed to compare for significance difference ($p < 0.05$) between micronutrients in the fortified food product and Standard Requirement. * Nutritive Reference Values (NRVs); Source: Lewis, (2019), NAFDAC (2021). * Not Detected (ND).

In Table 8, the mineral levels show that calcium levels were very low compared to the required 1000 mg/kg. Sodium and iron were inconsistently present across samples, with iron and calcium detected at low levels. Sodium and potassium levels varied between samples. However, there were no

significant differences ($p < 0.05$) in iron, sodium, and potassium levels compared to the standard requirement.

Table 9 shows that iron was present in all samples but below the required 50 mg/kg. Calcium was absent in some samples, and potassium levels were highly inconsistent. Iron levels were the highest among all tested foods (up to 152.77 mg/kg). While calcium was detected in some samples, it was undetectable in others. Potassium was found in one sample at high levels but absent in others.

In Table 10, calcium levels varied significantly, ranging from 182.32 to 1500.53 mg/kg, while potassium and magnesium were absent in some samples. Sodium, potassium, magnesium, and phosphorus levels were generally low, indicating significant differences ($p < 0.05$) compared to the standard requirements.

Table 8: Concentrations of Minerals in Fortified Pasta Samples compared with Standard Requirement.

Food Category	Sample Identification Number	Ca (mg/kg)	Fe (mg/kg)	Na (mg/kg)	K (mg/kg)
Pasta	PAS-01	100.95±0.28 ^a	6.55±0.43 ^a	1507.16± 0.48 ^a	100.95±0.28 ^a
	PAS-02	100.95±0.28 ^b	6.55±0.43 ^b	ND	ND
	PAS-03	ND	100.95±0.28 ^c	6.55±0.43 ^b	1507.16± 0.48 ^b
*NRVs (mg/kg)		1000.00 ^{a,b}	50.00 ^{a,b,c}	2000.00 ^{a,b}	2000.00 ^{a,b}

Key: Values were expressed as mean±standard deviation of triplicate measurements; *T-test was performed to compare for significance difference ($p < 0.05$) between micronutrients in the fortified food product and Standard Requirement. * Nutritive Reference Values (NRVs); Source: Lewis, (2019), NAFDAC (2021). * Not Detected (ND).

Table 9: Concentrations of Minerals in fortified Flour Samples compared with Standard Requirement.

Food Category	Sample Identification Number	Ca (mg/kg)	Fe (mg/kg)	K (mg/kg)	Zn (mg/kg)	Mg (mg/kg)	P (mg/kg)
Flour	FLO-01	ND	135.27±0.32 ^a	ND	201.88±0.55 ^a	25.96±0.40 ^a	363.22±0.30 ^a
	FLO-02	207.21±0.36 ^a	111.00±0.36 ^b	ND	207.05±0.28 ^b	ND	ND
	FLO-03	ND	136.78±0.30 ^c	2100.21±0.29 ^a	ND	27.24±0.33 ^b	367.06±0.62 ^b
	FLO-04	ND	152.77±0.38 ^d	ND	64.07±0.24 ^c	26.34±0.22 ^c	283.34±0.30 ^c
*NRVs (mg/kg)		1000.00 ^a	50.00 ^{a,b,c,d}	2000.00 ^a	30.00 ^{a,b,c}	310.00 ^{a,b,c}	1000.00 ^{a,b,c}

Key: Values were expressed as mean±standard deviation of triplicate measurements; *T-test was performed to compare for significance difference ($p < 0.05$) between micronutrients in the fortified food product and Standard Requirement. * Nutritive Reference Values (NRVs); Source: Lewis, (2019), NAFDAC (2021). * Not Detected (ND).

Table 10: Concentrations of Minerals in Fortified Vegetable Oil Samples compared with Standard Requirement.

Food Category	Sample Identification Number	Ca (mg/kg)	Na (mg/kg)	K (mg/kg)	Mg (mg/kg)	P (mg/kg)
Vegetable	VEO-01	1500.53± 0.74 ^a	ND	ND	ND	ND
Oil	VEO-02	182.32±0.45 ^b	803.17±0.95 ^a	472.72±0.31 ^a	14.96±0.30 ^a	1.05±0.01 ^a
	VEO-03	644.74±0.36 ^c	ND	ND	ND	2.61±0.14 ^b
*NRVs (mg/kg)		1000.00 ^{a,b,c}	2000.00 ^a	2000.00 ^a	310.00 ^a	1000.00 ^{a,b}

Key: Values were expressed as mean±standard deviation of triplicate measurements; *T-test was performed to compare for significance difference ($p < 0.05$) between micronutrients in the fortified food product and Standard Requirement. * Nutritive Reference Values (NRVs); Source: Lewis, (2019), NAFDAC (2021). * Not Detected (ND).

Table 11 shows that iron was only found in one sample (SUG-02), with sodium and potassium levels being inconsistent across samples. Iron was present in only one sample (SUG-02, 114.25

mg/kg), while sodium and potassium were inconsistently detected. The mineral content in this table showed significant differences ($p < 0.05$) compared to the standard requirements.

Finally, Table 12 reveals that sodium levels were significantly above the required standard, while iodine levels were much lower than the standard of 20 mg/kg. Sodium was extremely high (6832.97 mg/kg) compared to the 2000 mg/kg standard,

while iodine was far below the required 20 mg/kg. Mineral levels showed significant differences ($p < 0.05$) when compared to the standard requirements.

Table 11: Concentrations of Minerals in Fortified Sugar Samples compared with Standard Requirement.

Food Category	Sample Identification Number	Ca (mg/kg)	Fe (mg/kg)	Na (mg/kg)	K (mg/kg)	P(mg/kg)
Sugar	SUG-01	ND	ND	322.69±0.26 ^a	ND	28.13±0.36 ^a
	SUG-02	175.48±0.37 ^a	114.25±0.35 ^a	ND	697.07±0.60 ^a	ND
*NRVs (mg/kg)		1000.00 ^a	50.00 ^a	2000.00 ^a	2000.00 ^a	1000.00 ^a

Key: Values were expressed as mean±standard deviation of triplicate measurements; *T-test was performed to compare for significance difference ($p < 0.05$) between micronutrients in the fortified food product and Standard Requirement. * Nutritive Reference Values (NRVs); Source: Lewis, (2019), NAFDAC (2021). * Not Detected (ND).

Table 12: Concentrations of Minerals in Fortified Salt Samples compared with Standard Requirement.

Food Category	Sample Identification Number	Na (mg/kg)	I (mg/kg)
Salt	SLT-01	6832.97±0.67 ^a	3.57±0.14 ^a
*NRVs (mg/kg)		2000.00 ^a	20.00 ^a

Key: Values were expressed as mean±standard deviation of triplicate measurements; *T-test was performed to compare for significance difference ($p < 0.05$) between micronutrients in the fortified food product and Standard Requirement. * Nutritive Reference Values (NRVs); Source: Lewis, (2019), NAFDAC (2021). * Not Detected (ND).

4.0 Discussion

The results of this study indicate significant discrepancies between the labeled micronutrient content of fortified foods and the actual nutrient levels determined through laboratory analysis. These findings align with previous research highlighting inconsistencies in food fortification programs and the need for stricter regulatory enforcement.

Vitamin Analysis

In (Table 2), the study revealed that Vitamin A levels in fortified rice ranged from 798.30 IU/kg to undetectable levels, far below the mandated 25,000 IU/kg. This trend is consistent with findings who reported that many fortified foods in low-income countries fail to meet regulatory standards due to inadequate quality control and poor storage conditions. Similar deficiencies were observed in fortified vegetable oils, where Vitamin A levels ranged from 383.60 IU/kg to 504.90 IU/kg, significantly below the required 20,000 IU/kg and there is significant differences ($p < 0.05$) between the Laboratory analysis and the standard requirements [26, 27].

Furthermore, Vitamin B1 and B3 levels in rice (Table 2), pasta (Table 3), and flour (Table 4) samples were

considerably lower than the Standard 6 mg/kg and 45 mg/kg, respectively. These results parallel the findings of [28,29], who noted that large-scale fortification programs for flour and cereals often fall short of expected nutrient levels due to processing losses and poor monitoring.

Minerals Analysis

The iron content in fortified rice samples (Table 7) varied widely, from 6.55 mg/kg to 152.77 mg/kg, reflecting inconsistencies reported in similar studies [28]. In some cases, iron levels exceeded the recommended amounts, raising concerns about potential health risks associated with excessive iron consumption. Similarly, iodine levels in fortified salt (Table 12) were found to be lower than the 20 mg/kg requirement, reinforcing concerns raised about the stability of iodine in salt over time and the need for improved fortification techniques [29].

Zinc, Magnesium, and Potassium levels also varied significantly across different food categories. The inadequate presence of these micronutrients has been noted in previous studies [30, 31], which suggested that fortification methods must be tailored to ensure stability and bioavailability.

Similar studies conducted in Sub-Saharan Africa, such as those documented challenges in achieving optimal fortification levels, particularly in staple foods. The discrepancies observed in this study highlight the need for improved compliance with national fortification standards, as seen in developed nations where stricter monitoring and enforcement mechanisms are in place [26, 31].

The findings underscore the urgent need for enhanced regulatory oversight, as well as the adoption of best practices from successful fortification programs globally. Lessons from the United States and Europe suggest that routine laboratory testing, improved packaging, and proper storage conditions can significantly enhance the effectiveness of fortification efforts [32, 33].

Food fortification remains a vital strategy for combating micronutrient deficiencies, the observed inconsistencies in this study emphasize the need for stringent enforcement of fortification regulations and continuous quality monitoring. Further research should focus on developing more stable fortification methods to improve nutrient retention in fortified foods over time [34].

5.0 Conclusion

The study assessed the micronutrient content in fortified foods sold in Kebbi State by comparing laboratory analysis results with the claims made on product labels. The research aimed to determine whether these fortified foods met the required nutritional standards set by regulatory bodies like NAFDAC [35].

Many fortified food samples contained significantly lower vitamin concentrations than required by national standards. In rice samples (Table 2), Vitamin A was undetected in most brands, despite label claims that the product contained it. The Standard requirement for Vitamin A in rice is 25,000 IU/kg, but the actual measured values in rice samples were either undetectable or significantly lower.

Pasta samples (Table 3) showed similar discrepancies, the Standard requirement for Vitamin A is 25,000 IU/kg, the actual measured values were between 478.98 IU/kg and 489.35 IU/kg, far below the standard. Flour samples (Table 4) also exhibited inconsistencies. Vitamin A was supposed to be present at 25,000 IU/kg, but actual values were either undetected or much lower (ranging from 509.04 IU/kg to 581.62 IU/kg). Vegetable oil (Table 5) and sugar (Table 6) samples contained much lower Vitamin A than required, with sugar samples

showing values of 447.48 IU/kg and 407.44 IU/kg, compared to the Standard requirement of 26,000 IU/kg.

Minerals such as Calcium (Ca), Iron (Fe), Sodium (Na), and Potassium (K) were analyzed, and major variations were found. In rice samples (Table 7), the measured Calcium content ranged from 100.95 mg/kg to 178.84 mg/kg, significantly lower than the expected fortification levels and significant differences ($p < 0.05$) from the standard requirements.

Iron concentrations in rice varied widely, with some samples containing as little as 6.55 mg/kg, while others reached 76.78 mg/kg, showing a lack of standardization. Sodium and Potassium levels were also inconsistent, with some rice samples having no detectable sodium or potassium, despite label claims.

Similar inconsistencies were found in other fortified food groups, including flour, pasta, and vegetable oils. According to the national fortification regulations (NAFDAC, 2021), fortified foods must meet specific micronutrient levels. The study found that many samples failed to meet these requirements, meaning that consumers were not getting the expected nutritional benefits from these products.

This raises concerns about regulatory enforcement, quality control, and consumer protection in the Nigerian food industry. The study highlights significant shortcomings in the fortification of food products sold in Kebbi State. The failure of many fortified foods to meet Standard nutritional levels presents a serious public health concern, as it could contribute to micronutrient deficiencies in the population. Addressing these discrepancies requires better regulation, industry compliance, and public awareness to ensure that fortified foods genuinely meet the dietary needs of consumers.

6.0 Recommendations

For effectiveness of food fortification programs and ensuring that fortified foods sold in Kebbi State meet their intended nutritional goals. It is recommended that:

- Authorities should enhance monitoring and enforcement of fortification standards to ensure that manufacturers comply with required micronutrient levels.
- Regular independent laboratory analysis should be conducted to verify the accuracy of labeled claims and prevent discrepancies.

- Food producers should be mandated to provide accurate and transparent nutritional information, validated through routine testing.
- Consumers should be educated about the importance of micronutrients and the need to demand quality fortified foods.
- Training programs should be provided for food manufacturers on best practices for food fortification and quality control.
- Government agencies, research institutions, and health organizations should collaborate to ensure continuous assessment and improvement of fortified food products.

7.0 Conflict of Interest

The authors declared no conflict of interest.

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